

EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH ON $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}/\text{ZrO}_2$ EUTECTIC CERAMIC *IN SITU* COMPOSITE WITH LASER ZONE REMELTING

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ABSTRACT

With the melting point above 1800°C and various excellent properties even close to the melting point, alumina-rare earth multiphase eutectic *in situ* composite and its preparation method have aroused much attention in recent years. With the laser zone remelting technique, this paper reports the experimental research on the rapid solidification character of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}/\text{ZrO}_2$ ternary eutectic ceramic *in situ* composite. The relationship between the eutectic microstructure and the processing parameters is studied, and the mechanical property of the composite is preliminarily investigated. The results show that: (1) With the processing parameters adjusted properly, the ternary $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}/\text{ZrO}_2$ eutectic has homogeneous and coupled lamellar microstructure with lamellar spacing less than 0.3µm. (2) The maximum hardness reaches 18.67GPa and the room-temperature fracture toughness is $8.0\pm 2.0 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$.

Keywords: $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}/\text{ZrO}_2$, eutectic ceramic, *in situ* composite, laser remelting

INTRODUCTION

Generally speaking, the oxide ceramic cannot be applied as high-temperature structural material for its sensitivity to the plastic deformation. However, as it has excellent oxidation and corrosion resistance at elevated temperature, the oxide ceramic could be the preference choice served at the high-temperature oxidizing atmosphere over a long period of time. The oxide ceramic is very hopeful to become the thermostructural material with outstanding mechanical properties even close to its melting temperature if its mechanical property especially the room-temperature ductility could be evidently improved [1].

As the eutectic phases are all grown simultaneously from the melt, the manmade toughening or strengthening fibre and the corresponding composite technique which are necessary to traditional manmade composite are all discarded, while the artificial interface of matrix/fibre is substituted by the inherent matrix/second phase interface. With the inherent phase interface and the convenient microstructure control, eutectic *in situ* composite possesses a lot of characters such as simple processing technique, high thermodynamic stability of constituent phases, uniform and regular phase distribution, well-knit phase interface, high microstructure controllability, excellent property, strong anisotropic performance and integrative design of structure and function. Meanwhile, as the cavity and the interface amorphous phase which are very common in the traditionally sintered ceramics are either greatly reduced or even eliminated, the densification degree and the texture degree are all increased, which is much helpful to the elevation and stability of the mechanical property.

Since Viechnicki [2] took the lead in research of the directionally solidified $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}$ eutectic in 1969, Al_2O_3 -based eutectic *in situ* composite and its preparation technique have always been focused on due to its melting point above 1800°C and various excellent proper-

ties. However, it is since later 1990s when the high structural stability up to near the melting temperature was reported [3], the directionally solidified oxide eutectic *in situ* composite has been really attached great importance to [4~6]. More recently, much attention has been given to $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2$ ternary eutectic [7~9] in order to further improve the property of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ or $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2$ binary eutectic, which is very similar to the progress from monophase to multiphase of the metal alloy. With the laser zone remelting technique, this paper reports the experimental research on the rapid solidification character of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}/\text{ZrO}_2$ ternary eutectic ceramic *in situ* composite. The relationship between the eutectic microstructure and the processing parameters is studied. The hardness and the room-temperature fracture toughness of the as-solidified composite are preliminarily investigated by micro-indentation method.

EXPERIMENTAL

With the high purity (>4N) nano-powders of Al_2O_3 , Y_2O_3 and ZrO_2 , the $\Phi 7\text{mm}\times 30\text{mm}$ primary samples are prepared after mixing, pressing and sintering at 1500°C . The mole fraction of the composition is $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2=65.8/15.6/18.6$. With 5kW ROFIN-SINAR850 CO_2 laser, the laser zone remelting experiment is carried out in a vacuum chamber. The sample is moved by the numerically-controlled worktable with 5-axis and 4-direction coupled motion to realize the laser beam scanning along the sample axis. The sample is solidified just behind the melting zone. The microstructure and the component of the composite are determined by SEM, EDX and XRD. The hardness and the fracture toughness are determined by Vickers indentation technique on the polished surface of the composite, using applied load of 4.9N. The indentation size and the crack length are measured by optical microscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure

The eutectic microstructure is strongly affected by the scanning rate and the power density of the laser beam. As the laser absorptivity of the oxide is larger than 60%, only small power density is needed. The scanning rate directly determining the cooling rate has strong effect on the microstructure of the eutectic. The experiments show that under the Ar atmosphere with the laser power density of 190~220W, the scanning rate of 0.08~0.4mm/s and the beam diameter of 4mm, the crackless samples with smooth surface and high density can be obtained. Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively show the microstructure morphology and the phase constituent of the *in situ* composite. It can be seen that the composite is composed of coupled Al_2O_3 (the black), YAG (the grey) and ZrO_2 (the white) monocrystal phases without any other phases between them.

It can be clearly seen from Fig. 1(a) that the eutectic colonies grow along the scanning direction when the scanning rate is 0.4mm/s. As the temperature gradient of the solidification interface during the laser zone remelting can be high as $10^4\sim 10^5\text{K/cm}$ [10], the coupled growth of the ternary eutectic forms the layered microstructure with zirconia appeared as lamellar interphase between layers of alumina and yttrium aluminium garnet, shown as Fig. 1(b). The zirconia phases also present either as rods to be surrounded by the alumina or as tiny block to locate at the edge of the YAG due to the different cooling conditions at different places. Deep acid erosion reveals superfine lamellas of the cubic yttria stabilized zirconia with the lamellar spacing less than $0.3\mu\text{m}$, which is approximately 1/10 of the binary $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}$ eutectic spacing [11], shown as Fig. 1(c). The addition of zirconia and the rapid solidification character of

laser zone remelting promote together to change the entangled pattern of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}$ eutectic [4, 11] to more ordered eutectic structure.

Fig. 1 Solidification microstructure of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}/\text{ZrO}_2$ ternary eutectic (a) eutectic colony growth (b) layered microstructure (c) superfine lamellas of ZrO_2

Fig. 2 Phase constituent of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}/\text{ZrO}_2$ ternary eutectic

Vickers hardness and fracture toughness

Fig. 3 shows an indentation on the longitudinal section of a sample with cracks emerging from the corners. The hardness and the room-temperature fracture toughness of the composite can be calculated from the micro-indentation test data using the following equations:

$$H = k_1 P / a^2 \quad (1)$$

$$K_{IC} = k_2(E/H)^{2/5}(P/a^{1/2}) \quad (2)$$

where H is the Vickers hardness, K_{IC} is the fracture toughness, E is the Young's Modulus of the material, P is the indentation load, a is half indentation diagonal, l is the crack length, and k_1 and k_2 are the dimensionless constants. The calculation shows that the maximum hardness of the composite is 18.67GPa, which is intervenient between those of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}$ (16.3GPa) [12] and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2$ (20GPa) [13]. The calculation result also indicates that the room-temperature fracture toughness of the composite reaches $8.0 \pm 2.0 \text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, which is higher than those of monocrystal Al_2O_3 ($2.4 \text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$), monocrystal YAG ($3.0 \text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$) and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}$ eutectic ($2.0 \sim 4.0 \text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$) [4, 5, 12], but is very close to the data of Calderon-Moreno ($9.0 \pm 2.0 \text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$) [9]. This means that with the addition of ZrO_2 into the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ to form the ternary eutectic, the fracture toughness of the eutectic ceramic *in situ* composite can be effectively increased by a large margin. Meanwhile, the reduced phase size and spacing due to the rapid solidification of the laser zone remelting, effectively arrests the crack growth and propagation.

Fig. 3 Indentation on the longitudinal section of an $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}/\text{ZrO}_2$ ternary eutectic sample

CONCLUSION

With the laser zone remelting technique, the crackless samples of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}/\text{ZrO}_2$ ternary eutectic ceramic *in situ* composite with smooth surface and high density can be obtained. The coupled growth of the ternary eutectic forms the homogeneous layered microstructure with zirconia appeared as lamellar interphase between layers of alumina and yttrium aluminium garnet. The zirconia phases also present either as rods to be surrounded by the alumina or as tiny block to locate at the edge of the YAG. The superfine lamellas of the cubic yttria stabilized zirconia with the lamellar spacing less than $0.3 \mu\text{m}$ are presented. No other phases and grain boundaries are found.

The maximum hardness and the room-temperature fracture toughness of the composite measured by the micro-indentation test are 18.67GPa and $8.0 \pm 2.0 \text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ respectively. The addition of zirconia and the fine rapid solidification microstructure have contributed to the improved mechanical properties. Further investigation on the mechanisms of the eutectic growth and the fracture should be carried out.

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